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A STUDY ON AWARENESS OF GOVERNMENT SCHEMES AMONG WOMEN ENTREPRENEURS ENGAGED IN MICRO ENTERPRISES OF MEERUT CITY

Ms. Anshika Verma¹ & Prof. Sonika Choudhary²

Research Scholar¹, Professor and Incharge²

Department of Home Science, Raghunath Girls' Post Graduate College,

Chaudhary Charan Singh University, Meerut-250001

Uttar Pradesh, India^{1&2}

Email- anshika.verma1809@gmail.com¹, sonikabhagatsingh11@gmail.com²

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ABSTRACT

The entrepreneurial spirit of the nation drives its progress and makes a major contribution to its overall development. The Indian government has recognized the need to uplift and empower women entrepreneurs and launched several schemes and programs to encourage more women to start their businesses that will not only help them financially but also promote their contribution to becoming partners in the nation's progress. If the benefits provided by these schemes are availed adequately, it will result in good transformation and have a greater impact on the businesses owned and operated by these women. This paper aimed to assess the awareness of the various development schemes and programs and its association with socio-demographic data and entrepreneurial profiles among women entrepreneurs of Meerut city that have been implemented by the government to support them. For the current investigation, the research was mainly based on primary data wherein the information was obtained from primary sources, such as women entrepreneurs, and secondary sources that were gathered from previously published articles, papers, journals, etc. The 100 registered female entrepreneurs were chosen as a sample using the convenience sampling method of non-probability sampling techniques. The self-structured questionnaire was utilized as a data collection tool, and the descriptive survey method was the research design employed in this study. The study concluded that the majority of the women entrepreneurs are not aware of the schemes and programs that are easily accessible to them; as a result, they cannot get profit from these schemes. The findings of the study recommended raising more awareness among women and motivating them to start small enterprises.

Key Words: awareness extent, government schemes, micro-enterprises, women entrepreneurs

INTRODUCTION

When women's status and standard of living are on a level with men's, a nation is considered to have undergone revolution. Jawaharlal Nehru, the first Prime Minister of India, famously remarked, "When a woman moves forward, the family moves, the village moves, and the nation moves." Keeping this in mind, women are therefore seen as the focal point of nation-building. In the marketplace and in society, women are consistently undervalued. Even if they have the capacity to confront and resolve the situation, they are prevented from obtaining quality healthcare, education, training, and employment possibilities. Although the number of women operating their

businesses is rising, their potential for entrepreneurship and socioeconomic achievements is still mostly unrealized. They are mostly engaged in micro-sized, informal, low-return, poor-productivity enterprises. Providing gender-responsive laws, services, and business settings is essential to encouraging women's companies to start and grow. This will assist in achieving gender equality, reducing poverty, and ensuring healthier economies and societies. It is unclear if women in microenterprises and small companies, especially in developing nations, are aware of and taking advantage of the government assistance programs that are accessible to them. Women entrepreneurs are those who own, start, and manage businesses that empower women and improve their economic standing and standing in society. Due to a variety of economic constraints, women are now more likely than ever to pursue entrepreneurship and have come to the realization that working alongside males is the only way for them to survive and reach their full potential (Sangolagi & Alagawadi, 2016). In India, the business environment is evolving constantly due to the advancement of technology, modernization, industrialization, urbanization, the expansion of education, and government-initiated development programs. Under such circumstances, women's employment opportunities have risen significantly.

To support and encourage the growth of female entrepreneurs, the government has launched several policies, financing schemes, and entrepreneurship development programs. A few government initiatives for female entrepreneurs include the following:

- Pradhan Mantri MUDRA Yojana
- Uttar Pradesh Skill Development Mission
- Trade Related Entrepreneurship Assistance and Development Scheme (TREAD)
- Annapurna Scheme
- Mahila Udyam Nidhi (MUN) Yojana offered by SIDBI
- Stree Shakti Package, by State Bank of India
- Dena Shakti Scheme launched by Dena Bank
- Support to Training and Employment Program (STEP)
- Mahila-E-Haat” An online marketing platform
- ‘Nirbhaya Ek Pahal’ by Uttar Pradesh government
- ‘Synd Mahila Shakti Scheme’ by Canara Bank
- Women Entrepreneurship platform (WEP) 3.0 web platform
- District Industries Centre’(DIC) , by central government
- Credit Guarantee Fund Trust for Micro and Small Enterprises
- Nehru Rojgar Yojana
- Stand-up India’ Scheme

The Micro, Small, and Medium Enterprises Development (MSMED) Act of 2006 primarily divides companies into two sectors: manufacturing and services. Businesses that produce items are known as manufacturing companies. Service businesses are defined in terms of equipment investment and service providers. According to the 2025 revision, a microenterprise is a legally registered business with an investment in plant and machinery or equipment of no more than 2.5 crore and an annual turnover of no more than 10 crore. The government has effectively promoted entrepreneurship through various schemes, but women entrepreneurs often lack awareness and educational support regarding these initiatives. Awareness of the benefits is crucial for beneficiaries to take advantage of these programs. Unexpectedly, there is little discussion of this facet of Indian women entrepreneurs in the literature. This paper aims to determine the awareness

among Indian women entrepreneurs of government programs and schemes for their upliftment. It also offers suggestions for ways to increase awareness among women entrepreneurs.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Patni (2022) examined the awareness of government schemes among female entrepreneurs in selected wards (A-E) of South Mumbai. Utilizing an interview schedule method, data was collected from 300 respondents through the random sampling method. The study concluded that none of the female entrepreneurs were aware of government programs, indicating a significant issue. Arulmoorthy and Uma (2019) examined the awareness of the central government's entrepreneurship programs among women entrepreneurs using structured questionnaires filled out by 100 respondents. The survey employed simple percentage analysis to assess entrepreneurs' perceptions of the government plan. The results revealed that loans are generally viewed as a source of security for emerging enterprises. Sahoo et al. (2019) conducted a study titled "Women Entrepreneurs and Their Awareness Level towards Various Government Schemes." The data has been collected from 100 women business owners in the Khurda district of Odisha. Four distinct government programs for women were included in the study. A three-point Likert scale and chi-square test were used to interpret the data. The study's findings suggested that women should participate in more awareness campaigns and be encouraged to start small companies. Ashok et al. (2018) investigated women's awareness and access to government schemes for promoting entrepreneurship. The results revealed a mean score of 84.79, with an average of 3.26. Respondents scoring above 3.26 demonstrated full awareness and access to these schemes, whereas those below this score showed less awareness and access. Shiralashetti (2013) conducted a study on 1250 women entrepreneurs in North Karnataka. Statistical tools such as percentage analysis, scaling procedure, and chi-square were used to interpret and analyze the data. The study recommended that women entrepreneurs should be encouraged to obtain self-income and made more aware of the advantages of government programs.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

- To assess the socio-demographic data of the women entrepreneurs of Meerut city.
- To assess the entrepreneurial profile of the women entrepreneurs of Meerut city.
- To find out the association between the socio-demographic data, entrepreneurial profile and the awareness of government schemes of women entrepreneurs.

HYPOTHESIS

H₁: There is significant association between the socio-demographic data, entrepreneurial profile and the awareness of government schemes of women entrepreneurs.

H₀: There is no significant association between the socio-demographic data, entrepreneurial profile and the awareness of government schemes of women entrepreneurs.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Locale: Meerut city of Uttar Pradesh, India.

Research Design: The research design used in this study was the descriptive survey method.

Sample size and sampling technique: The convenience sampling technique of the non-probability sampling was used to select a sample of 100 registered female entrepreneurs in Meerut city.

Data collection tool: Both primary and secondary sources of data were used in the present study. The self-structured questionnaire with closed-ended questions and statements has been utilized to collect primary data. Secondary data for the study have been gathered from different journals, magazines, official websites, and relevant research and review articles.

Data interpretation and analysis: Data have been analyzed using frequency and percentage analysis. A chi-square test was employed to find out the association between the socio-demographic data, entrepreneurial factors, and the awareness of government schemes.

Fig.-1: Flow chart of the conducted study

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table1: Distribution of sample women entrepreneurs on the basis of socio-demographic data and entrepreneurial profile.

Variables	Category	Frequency (n=100)
Age (years)	20-30	7
	31-40	67
	41-50	17
	51-60	9
Educational qualification	Illiterate	1
	Upper Primary	4
	High school	7
	Intermediate	17
	Graduation	39
	Post-graduation	32
Marital status	Married	89
	Unmarried	7
	Widow	4
Religion	Hindu	84
	Muslim	10
	Sikh	5
	Christian	1
Category	General	54
	OBC	38
	SC	8
Monthly Income (Rs.)	below 10000	11
	10001-20000	29
	20001-30000	19
	30001-40000	6
	40001-50000	9
	Above 50000	26
Type of family	Joint	71
	Nuclear	29
Type of ownership	Sole proprietorship	98
	Partnership	2
Nature of enterprises	Manufacturing Units	26
	Service Units	74
Source of investment in business	Investment of own savings	66
	Taken loan from banks	24
	Borrowed from friends and relatives	6
	Government loan schemes	4
Years of business experience	0-5	34

	6-10	38
	11-15	19
	16-20	6
	21-25	1
	26-30	2
Working Hours per day	less than 5 hours	4
	5-8 hours	38
	8-10 hours	58
Types of industries	Bakeries	3
	Beauty/spa/cosmetic center	41
	Educational coaching center	4
	General store	9
	Readymade garment shop	10
	Sports shops	3
	Tailoring/boutique	23
	Any other	7

Source: field survey computed data

Table 1 reveals that 67% of respondents were aged 31-40 years, and 7% of respondents were between 20 and 30 years old, indicating a higher proportion of early adulthood respondents compared to younger or elderly respondents. More than 30% of the respondents were of graduate and postgraduate level, and only one percent has been found to be illiterate. Although the respondents were found to be well educated, still they were not aware of the entrepreneurship-related government schemes. The majority of the respondents, 89%, were married, with 7% unmarried and 4% of the respondents being sadly widowed. The majority of respondents, 84%, were Hindu, and only 1% was Christian. The majority of the respondents (54%) were General Caste, followed by Other Backward Class (38%), and only 8% belonged to the SC category.

The survey revealed that the majority of the respondents (29%) had a monthly income in the range of Rs. 10000-20000, followed by 26% who had an income above Rs. 50000, and the rest had a monthly income below Rs. 10000 and in the range of Rs. 20000-50000. The majority of the respondents (71%) belong to joint families, and the rest of them (29%) live in nuclear families, indicating that those who live in joint families get support from family while balancing their personal and professional lives. The study revealed that 98% of the enterprises owned by the respondents belong to sole proprietorships; only 2% of the enterprises were being run under partnership. The results revealed that 74% of the enterprises were service units, and the rest of the 26% belonged to manufacturing units, indicating the ability to run service units with more ease, as stated by the respondents. It has been found that 66% of the respondents used their own savings to invest in business, 24% have taken loans from banks, 6% borrowed money from their friends and relatives, and only 4% have availed themselves of the benefit of government loan schemes for investment. The majority of the respondents (38%) had 6-10 years of experience, and only three had more than 20 years of experience. A higher number (58%) of the respondents committed 8-10 hours, 38% devoted 5-8 hours, and 4% of the respondents devoted less than 5 hours (operating coaching institutions) every day to their business activities. Beauty, spa, and cosmetics have drawn the highest percentage of female entrepreneurs (41%), followed by boutiques and tailoring (23%), general stores (9%), educational coaching centers (4%), bakeries and sports stores (3% each),

ready-made clothing stores (10%), and other various businesses that were found to be run by 7% of women.

Table 2- Age* Awareness of Scheme

Variable		Awareness of Scheme		Total	Pearson Chi-Square		
		Yes	No		Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Age	20 to 30 years	2	5	7	1.235 ^a	3	.745
	31 to 40 Years	30	37	67			
	41 to 50 years	7	10	17			
	51 to 60 years	5	4	9			
Total		44	56	100			

Note-Relationship is NOT Significant, *df = degree of freedom

Table 2 reveals that there is no significant relationship between the age and awareness of respondents for government schemes ($p > 0.05$).

Table 3- Educational Qualification * Awareness of Scheme

Variable		Awareness of Scheme		Total	Pearson Chi-Square		
		Yes	No		Value	Df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Educational Qualification	Illiterate	0	1	1	3.484 ^a	5	.626
	Upper primary	2	2	4			
	High school	4	3	7			
	Intermediate	10	7	17			
	Graduation	15	24	39			
	Post-Graduation	13	19	32			
Total		44	56	100			

Note-Relationship is NOT Significant, *df = degree of freedom

Table 3 reveals that there is no significant relationship between the educational qualification and awareness of respondents for government schemes ($p > 0.05$).

Table 4- Marital Status * Awareness of Scheme

Variable		Awareness of Scheme		Total	Pearson Chi-Square		
		Yes	No		Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Marital Status	Married	42	47	89	4.187 ^a	2	.123
	Unmarried	2	5	7			
	Widow	0	4	4			
Total		44	56	100			

Note-Relationship is NOT Significant, *df = degree of freedom

Table 4 reveals that there is no significant relationship between the marital status and awareness of respondents for government schemes ($p > 0.05$).

Table 5- Religion * Awareness of Scheme

Variable		Awareness of Scheme			Total	Pearson Chi- Square		
						Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided) P ≤ 0.05
Religion	Hindu	32	52	84	9.864 ^a	3	.020 (Sig*)	
	Muslim	8	2	10				
	Sikh	4	1	5				
	Christian	0	1	1				
Total		44	56	100				

Note-Relationship is Significant at .05-level. , *df = degree of freedom

Table 5 reveals that there is significant relationship between religion and awareness of respondents for government schemes ($p < 0.05$).

Table 6- Category * Awareness of Scheme

Variable		Awareness of Scheme			Total	Pearson chi- square		
		Yes	No	Total		Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided) p > 0.05
Category	General	23	31	54	1.771 ^a	2	.413	
	OBC	19	19	38				
	SC	2	6	8				
Total		44	56	100				

Note-Relationship is NOT Significant, *df = degree of freedom

Table 6 reveals that there is no significant relationship between the category and awareness of respondents for government schemes ($p > 0.05$).

Table 7- Monthly Income* Awareness of Scheme

Variable		Awareness of Scheme			Total	Pearson Chi-Square		
		Yes	No	Total		Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Monthly Income	Below 10000	5	6	11	4.046 ^a	5	.543	
	10001-20000	15	14	29				
	20001-30000	8	11	19				
	30001-40000	4	2	6				
	40001-50000	2	7	9				

Above 50000	10	16	26			
Total	44	56	100			

Note-Relationship is NOT Significant, *df = degree of freedom

Table 7 reveals that there is no significant relationship between the monthly income and awareness of respondents for government schemes ($p>0.05$).

Table 8- Type of family * Awareness of Scheme

Variable		Awareness of Scheme		Total	Pearson Chi-Square		
		Yes	No		Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Family Type	Joint	32	39	71	.114 ^a	1	.736
	Nuclear	12	17	29			
Total		44	56	100			

Note-Relationship is NOT Significant, *df = degree of freedom

Table 8 reveals that there is no significant relationship between the type of family and awareness of respondents for government schemes ($p>0.05$).

Table 9- Type of Ownership * Awareness of Scheme

Variable		Awareness of Scheme		Total	Pearson Chi-Square		
		Yes	No		Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Ownership	Sole Proprietorship	42	56	98	2.597 ^a	1	.107
	Partnership	2	0	2			
Total		44	56	100			

Note-Relationship is NOT Significant, *df = degree of freedom

Table 9 reveals that there is no significant relationship between the type of ownership and awareness of respondents for government schemes ($p>0.05$).

Table 10- Nature of Enterprises * Awareness of Scheme

Variable		Awareness of Scheme		Total	Pearson Chi-Square		
		Yes	No		Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Nature of Enterprises	Manufacturing	9	17	26	1.256 ^a	1	.262
	Service	35	39	74			
Total		44	56	100			

Note-Relationship is NOT Significant, *df = degree of freedom

Table 10 reveals that there is no significant relationship between the nature of enterprises and awareness of respondents for government schemes ($p>0.05$).

Table 11- Source of Investment * Awareness of Scheme

Variable		Awareness of Scheme		Total	Pearson Chi-Square		
		Yes	No		Value	Df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Source of Investment	Own savings	28	38	66	7.517 ^a	3	.057
	Taken loan from banks	8	16	24			
	Borrowed from friends and family	4	2	6			
	Government loan schemes	4	0	4			
Total		44	56	100			

Note-Relationship is NOT Significant, *df = degree of freedom

Table 11 reveals that there is no significant relationship between the source of investment and awareness of respondents for government schemes ($p>0.05$).

Table 12- Years of Experience * Awareness of Scheme

Variable		Awareness of Scheme		Total	Pearson Chi-Square		
		Yes	No		Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Years of Experience	0-5	17	17	34	4.983 ^a	5	.418
	6-10	14	24	38			
	11-15	10	9	19			
	16-20	2	4	6			
	21-25	1	0	1			
	26-30	0	2	2			
Total		44	56	100			

Note-Relationship is NOT Significant, *df = degree of freedom

Table 12 reveals that there is no significant relationship between the years of experience and awareness of respondents for government schemes ($p>0.05$).

Table 13 Working hours per day * Awareness of Scheme

Variable		Awareness of Scheme		Total	Pearson Chi-Square		
		Yes	No		Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Working hours per day	Less than 5 hours	4	0	4	6.722 ^a	2	.035
	5-8 hours	13	25	38			
	8-10 hours	27	31	58			
Total		44	56	100			

Note-Relationship is Significant at .05-level. , *df = degree of freedom

Table 13 reveals that there is significant relationship between the working hours per day and awareness of respondents for government schemes ($p < 0.05$).

Table 14- Types of industries * Awareness of Scheme

Variable		Awareness of Scheme			Pearson Chi-Square		
		Yes	No	Total	Value	Df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Type of industries	Bakeries	1	2	3	6.808 ^a	7	.449
	Beauty/Spa/Cosmetic center	23	18	41			
	Educational coaching center	2	2	4			
	General store	3	6	9			
	Readymade garment shop	2	8	10			
	Sports shop	1	2	3			
	Tailoring/Boutique	8	15	23			
	Any other	4	3	7			
Total		44	56	100			

Note-Relationship is NOT Significant, *df = degree of freedom

Table 14 reveals that there is no significant relationship between the types of industries and awareness of respondents for government schemes ($p > 0.05$).

Chi-square test results indicate that there is statistically no significant association between age, educational qualification, marital status, category, monthly income, type of family, type of ownership, nature of enterprises, source of investment in business, years of business experience, types of industries, and awareness of government schemes at the 5% significance level ($p > 0.05$). Contradictory results were found that age, education, caste, marital status, family size, and years of business operation are the demographic parameters that have an association with the awareness of women entrepreneurs at a 5% level of significance (Sahoo et al., 2019), and there is a significant relationship between educational qualification and awareness of government schemes among women entrepreneurs (Kiruthiga & Sankar, 2023). In contrast, the results of this study found that there is a statistically significant association between religion and working hours per day and awareness of government schemes at the 5% level of significance ($p < 0.05$); this suggests that entrepreneurs with longer working hours are more likely to attend workshops, seminars, and trade meetings that disseminate information, and their interaction with suppliers, customers, banks, self-help groups, etc., increases their knowledge about government schemes.

A significant association was found between religion and awareness of government schemes; this suggests community support and networks that actively share information, the role of religious institutions that act as information hubs, and religious practices may also influence and encourage women’s mobility, participation in economic activities, and government programs. So, the results provide partial support for the null hypothesis. Therefore, the null hypothesis failed to be rejected for variables such as age, educational qualification, marital status, category, monthly income, type of family, type of ownership, nature of enterprises, source of investment in business,

years of experience, and types of industries but was rejected for variables such as religion and working hours per day.

LIMITATIONS OF THE STUDY

The survey was confined to 100 registered female entrepreneurs who reside and run their businesses in the urban region of Meerut City, so the sample size doesn't represent the population outside of this region. Women entrepreneurs under 20 and over 60, as well as those from rural regions, were not included in the study.

CONCLUSION AND SUGGESTIONS

According to the study, conducted in Meerut city, very few women entrepreneurs were aware of some government schemes like the Mudra Yojana, Cent Kalyani Scheme, and Annapurna Scheme, while most of them were unaware. It is evident that very few women are taking advantage of these initiatives. Based on the study's findings, it can be concluded that informing female entrepreneurs about government initiatives requires targeted techniques. Campaigns, seminars, and workshops with a community focus can effectively disseminate knowledge, and women should also be encouraged to take part in more awareness campaigns. Awareness will be increased when the information is shared in regional languages on social media and digital channels. Furthermore, organizing mentorship programs and networking events will create a community of support that encourages resource sharing and increased utilization. Policies related to the upliftment of women entrepreneurs must be periodically reviewed to examine their effects on the success rate of women entrepreneurs. Government schemes can be made more accessible by streamlining application procedures, clarifying guidelines, and offering assistance. This study also serves as a foundation for future research that can examine different aspects of women entrepreneurship.

RECOMMENDATIONS FOR FUTURE RESEARCH

There is always room for further study by exploring a number of more in-depth topics related to women entrepreneurship. Research can also be conducted on the following recommendations:

- Comparison of the awareness and availability of government programs between rural and urban women entrepreneurs.
- Examining regional or state-specific differences to see how local governance contributes to implementation.
- Examination can be done on how socioeconomic status, age, and education affect schemes' awareness and usage.
- Determination of the discrepancies between scheme awareness and actual utilization, looking into the causes of underutilization.
- Research can also be conducted on how social media and digital literacy might raise awareness among female entrepreneurs.
- Examine the awareness levels of particular groups, such as underprivileged women and micro-entrepreneurs.

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